

EFFECT OF FIBRE AND MATRIX TYPE ON THE POST-IMPACT COMPRESSION
STRENGTH OF LAMINATED
POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the work reported in this paper was to measure and compare the post-impact compression strengths, over a range of incident impact energies, of three materials (glass / epoxy, carbon / toughened epoxy and carbon / polyetheretherketone), with a view to determining the role of matrix and fibres on the properties. By plotting damage width as a function of incident impact energy the resistance to the initiation and propagation of impact damage can be assessed. By plotting compression strength as a function of damage width the damage tolerance of the materials can be assessed. The results show that matrix effects control the impact damage while fibre effects dominate damage tolerance.

KEYWORDS: Compression After Impact; Strength; Low Velocity Impact; Delamination; Damage Tolerance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminated polymer composite materials are susceptible to damage resulting from low energy impact events. Delamination is a major damage mode and can seriously effect the residual compression strength of these materials. This is of particular concern to aircraft designers because impact damage can be caused by low energy impacts from hailstones, runway stones and dropped tools for example. Increasing importance is being placed on the results of compression after impact tests for both materials development and selection purposes. It is therefore important to be able to assess the significance of results generated by this test

procedure. In this paper the results of post-impact compression tests on three different materials will be reported. A method of interpreting the results which allows the resistance to damage and the damage tolerance of the three materials to be assessed will be presented.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The post-impact compression strengths of three materials were measured, details of the materials are shown in the table below:

Manufacturer / Material	Fibre	Matrix	Abbreviation
ICI / APC-2	Hercules, AS-4	Polyetheretherketone	APC
Ciba-Geigy / Fibredux 924C	Torayca, T800H	Toughened Epoxy	TCE
Ciba-Geigy / Fibredux 913G	'E' Glass	Epoxy	GRP

The tests were carried out on specimens with dimensions of 89 x 55 mm. A 16 ply, quasi-isotropic lay-up $([-45, 0, +45, 90]_{2s})$ was used, giving a nominal specimen thickness of 2 mm.

An instrumented dropweight impact machine was used to damage the specimens prior to compression testing. A striker weighing 3.96 kg with a 20 mm diameter hemispherical loading nose was used. The maximum incident impact energy used was approximately 15 J and was varied by changing the dropheight. The specimen was clamped between two plates, each with a 40 mm diameter circular opening. After impact the extent of damage in the carbon fibre reinforced materials was assessed using an ultrasonic C-scanning machine. The GRP specimens were not C-scanned since the damage was clearly visible to the naked eye, however, the specimens were back-lit to enhance visibility.

The compression tests were carried out at a loading rate of 0.3 mm / min, the specimens being supported in an anti-buckling guide (ABG) which is shown schematically in fig 1.

More complete details of the experimental methods used can be found in refs 1 and 2.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Impact Testing

It was possible to estimate the damage initiation energy for each material from the results of the instrumented impact tests. The force peak associated with the initiation of delamination damage was identified, and for each specimen the total amount of energy absorbed at this force peak was measured. By assuming that damage would just be initiated if the incident impact energy

were just equal to the absorbed energy at damage initiation, and averaging over all the specimens tested, a damage initiation energy was estimated. The energies required were TCE, 0.81 J (Standard Deviation (SD) 0.10 J); GRP, 1.05 J (SD 0.17 J) and APC, 2.54 J (SD 0.47 J). The higher initiation energy for the APC is attributed to its higher G_{IIc} and its ability to absorb energy in plastic deformation during the impact event. The APC material showed evidence of plastic deformation, both locally on the impacted surface, in the form of a small indentation, and in the form of a small dome on the un-impacted surface. In contrast the damage to the two epoxy based materials would be best described as barely visible, except for at the highest energy levels, where fibre spalling was evident on the rear face of the specimens. Most importantly sectioning of all three materials revealed that delamination was the major damage mode. The extent of delamination damage in the GRP specimens can be seen in fig 2 (a). (Note: the specimen numbers are printed in the top left-hand corner, and the incident impact energy in the bottom left-hand corner of each specimen). As expected the in-plane extent of damage increases as the incident impact energy is increased. The damage is induced mainly by bending stresses and is therefore limited to a maximum of 40 mm, which is the diameter of the support ring. It can also be seen in fig 2 (a) that the extent of delamination damage varies through the thickness of the specimen.

3.2 Compression Testing

The results of compression after impact tests are usually presented by plotting residual strength as a function of incident impact energy. Fig 3 shows the results for the three materials plotted in this way. For each material three previously undamaged specimens were tested in order to provide a base-line strength against which the results of the residual strength tests could be compared. A mean strength and nominal standard deviation were calculated for each material (nominal because five tests are usually required for a reasonable estimate of the standard deviation to be made). The following strengths were measured: TCE, 392.4 MPa (SD 45.7); APC, 421.8 MPa (SD 32.5) and GRP 265.0 MPa (SD 10.9). These specimens failed in two different ways - either by local buckling in the unsupported region between the ABG and the end loading plate (see fig 1) or by crushing at the end of the specimen. For the limited number of tests performed the measured strengths appeared to be independent of the failure mode. The undamaged strengths have also been plotted in fig 3, they have been shifted along the energy axis by an amount equal to the energy required to initiate impact damage. The error bars correspond to ± 1 standard deviation. The points indicate the approximate position on the graph where reductions in compression strength would first be expected to occur.

In fig 3 the two points for the APC material marked with an asterisk did not sustain any damage during the impact test and failed in the unsupported region of the specimen. The point for the TCE material marked with an asterisk relates to a specimen which did sustain impact damage, but still failed in the unsupported region of the specimen. The rest of the impacted specimens for all three materials failed through the impact damage during the compression test.

Comparison of figs 2 (a) and (b) shows that the impact damage propagated perpendicular to the loading direction during the compression test, with no growth in the loading direction. Ultrasonic C-scans revealed that the carbon fibre materials behaved in a similar manner. This confirms the observations made by Bishop and Dorey (3).

The graph of residual strength plotted as a function of incident impact energy clearly shows that, for a given incident impact energy, the APC material retains the highest residual compression strength. It is also interesting to note that the residual strength of the TCE and GRP materials are very similar, in spite of the fact that their initial strengths were very different. However, it is not possible to tell from fig 3 which of the materials is the most damage tolerant. This is because the response of the materials during both the impact and compression tests is combined on one graph. One way to overcome this problem is to separate the results for the two parts of the test. By plotting a measure of the damage after the impact event as a function of the incident impact energy the resistance of the material to the initiation and propagation of damage during impact can be assessed. The maximum width of delamination damage, measured parallel to the specimen ends, was chosen as the damage parameter. The justification for this is that, as was mentioned above, the impact damage propagates laterally during the compression test. The damage widths are plotted as a function of incident impact energy in fig 4. The GRP material was found to be slightly more resistant to the initiation and propagation of impact damage than the TCE material. The APC material was found to be much more resistant to the initiation and propagation of damage than the epoxy based materials.

The damage tolerance of the materials can be assessed by plotting the residual compression strength as a function of the impact damage width. The results for the three materials are shown in figs 5 (a) - (c). Initially a least squares method was used to obtain a regression line of compression strength on damage width for each material. Correlation coefficients (r) of 0.96, 0.92 and 0.98 were obtained for the TCE, APC and GRP materials respectively. Following from this (and assuming that the data is normally distributed) the 95% confidence and prediction intervals were calculated, these are plotted in figs 5 (a) - (c). The performance of the materials is compared in figs 6 (a) and (b) by plotting just the normalised 95% prediction intervals. The data was normalised with respect to the undamaged strengths. It can be seen that the APC and TCE materials retain almost identical proportions of their initial strength for a given extent of impact damage (fig 6 (a)). In comparison the GRP material retains a higher proportion of its initial strength (fig 6 (b)) and is therefore judged to be the more damage tolerant material.

4. DISCUSSION

The post impact compression test is widely considered to provide a measure of the damage tolerance of the material. In reality the results generated provide information on the resistance

of the laminate to both the formation of damage under out-of-plane impact and the subsequent propagation of that damage under a different set of loading conditions (in-plane compression). It is the latter set of properties which truly characterise the damage tolerance of the material. The relative damage resistance and damage tolerance of a laminate are obscured by the practice of presenting PICS results as compression strength versus impact energy. The approach adopted in this work, namely to identify a damage parameter and compare the damage parameter with impact energy and compression strength separately enables both performance areas to be assessed.

The selection of the width of delamination damage appears justified. A clear linear link between this parameter and compression strength is observed for all materials tested. The approach is also in line with other workers, notably Ilcewicz (4) who performed tests on larger specimens (using the Boeing fixture), which showed the damage diameter versus compression strength data to be following a curve rather than a straight line as in our case. This effect is probably due to differences in specimen size as the width of impact damage is restricted to 40 mm in this work. It should be noted that damage width and damage area are not necessarily interchangeable parameters as the damage is not always symmetrical and the extent of damage along the compression loading axis of the plate is not relevant as delaminations propagate sideways.

The results shown in figures 3-6 serve to highlight the relative importance of matrix and fibre in the various parts of the PICS test. The extent of the delamination damage formed during impact is clearly a function of the matrix (and presumably the interfacial bond strength). The two epoxy composites, one with a glass reinforcement (GRP) and one with T800 carbon fibres (TCE), exhibit similar damage widths while the thermoplastic APC exhibits a much reduced level of damage for comparable impact blows. The laminate properties responsible for the different performances may be speculated to include the relevant interlaminar toughness, G_{IIc} , and the ductility of the matrix whereby yielding is observed on the surface of the thermoplastic. Although a figure for the G_{IIc} of GRP is not available, literature data for a carbon / epoxy and APC are of the order of 0.65 KJ m^{-2} and 1.82 KJ m^{-2} respectively (5).

Consideration of the two carbon fibre reinforced laminates suggests that while the damage resistance of the system is critically dependant on the matrix, the damage tolerance is not. There appears to be no significant difference between the two materials on the basis of figure 6a. This is in some respects surprising, particularly if the propagation of damage during the compression is considered in terms of fracture mechanics concepts. Attempts to model the propagation of delamination damage during the compression test as a mode I or mixed mode I /mode II fracture event (see for example ref 6) have generally not been successful. The differences between the G_{Ic} properties of the two laminates are even greater than those between the G_{IIc} . The values are in the order of 1.5 KJ m^{-2} for APC compared to 0.3 KJ m^{-2} for a typical carbon / toughened epoxy material (7).

The difference in normalised compression behaviour of the glass fibre composite compared to the carbon fibres systems, as shown in figure 6b, suggests that in the compression phase of the

test it is the influence of the fibres that dominates. The reasons for the relative performance of laminates with different fibres have not as yet been identified. It is possible that the relevant property involved is the strain to failure of the fibres, which might explain the apparent superior performance of the glass fibre material. This however supposes failures involving massive and widespread fibre fracture which is not the case. A more plausible explanation might be linked to the relative modulus of the fibres. The consequence of impact damage is to create effectively a soft delaminated region in the midst of a stiff laminate. This will create a stress magnification at the interface between the two regions, maximised at the equator of the nominally circular soft zone, the magnitude of which will depend on the relative stiffnesses of the soft and stiff material (8). If delaminations between the carbon laminae reduce the local stiffness to a greater extent relative to the undamaged material than delaminations in glass fibre laminae, then the fibre effect will be explained without recourse to fracture mechanics. This approach is to be developed further in future publications.

5. CONCLUSIONS

For the particular set of impact and compression test conditions which were used for this work the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The use of a damage parameter such as damage width enables the PICS test to characterise laminates in terms of both their damage resistance and damage tolerance.
2. The post impact compression strength is clearly determined by the extent of the damage introduced in the initial impact
3. Matrix effects dominate the behaviour in the low energy impact part of the test by controlling the extent of delamination damage.
4. Fibre effects are dominant in controlling the residual compression strengths of the laminates, although the mechanisms responsible for this effect are not as yet understood.

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Figure 1. Schematic Diagram to show Compression Specimen Support Conditions

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Photographs showing Damage in GRP Specimens after (a) Impact and (b) Subsequent Compression Testing.

Figure 3. Compression Strength versus Incident Impact Energy.

Figure 4. Damage Width versus Incident Impact Energy.

Figure 5. Compression Strength versus Damage Width, 95% Confidence and Prediction Intervals for: (a) TCE, (b) APC and (c) GRP Materials.

Figure 6. Comparison of 95% Prediction Intervals for: (a) TCE and APC and (b) TCE and GRP Materials.

